

A Comprehensive Framework for Characterization and Simulation of Forming Processes

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Composites Forming Simulation Challenges

In automated deposition processes such as forming:

- The material undergoes large deformations
- There may be a large number of parts with evolving interactions (such as contact) between them:
 - Mould
 - Material layers
 - Diaphragm or punch
 - Grip holders
- Unlike sheet metal forming, the workpiece (laminates) is composed of multiple orthotropic material plies with different fibre orientations

Farnand et al (2017)*

* Farnand et al (2017), Micro-level mechanisms of fiber waviness and wrinkling during hot drape forming of unidirectional prepreg composites, Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing. ;103:168–77.

Physics-Based Forming Simulation

- Physics-based modelling is founded on our understanding of *causality* of events.
- The phenomena of interest are modelled using mathematical representations
- In Process Simulation, a physics-based model needs to include representations of:
 - **Material** being processed: its incoming state, its evolution when subjected to process conditions
 - **Process**: Sequence of events and boundary conditions
 - **Equipment**: Interaction of the equipment with material and its effect on process conditions

Key Deformation Mechanisms

Ply In-plane (axial, shear, locking)

Interlaminar (shear/friction, stick-slip, tack)

Ply Transverse Shear & Logrolling

Ply Bending & Buckling

Tool-Part interaction

Debulk & Consolidation

Prepreg Bending

Characterization Test

Bending characterization fixture installed in a rheometer

Top view of the double-roller design

- Fixture inspired by original Sachs(2014)* design
- Fixture features:
 - Double roller design: minimizing frictional effects and providing uniform bending moment
 - Fixed sample length
- Fully definable test conditions:
 - Temperature
 - Bending Rate
 - Bending Angle and Radius of curvature
 - Loading/Relaxation/Unloading

* U. Sachs (2014), Friction and bending in thermoplastic composites forming process, PhD Dissertation, Universiteit Twente.

For more information see: Lane et al (2023), Characterization testing of un-cured prepreg fabrics for forming process. Proceedings of SAMPE Seattle

Prepreg Bending

Loading

Relaxation

Prepreg Bending

Constitutive Modelling: Non-linear Viscoelastic

- Fiber micro buckling is observed in bending samples
- This inspired development of a non-linear viscoelastic model that is schematically represented as a hinge on a viscoelastic bed

Prepreg Tack

Characterization Test

- Tack is the measure of the resistance to separation of two surfaces
- A prepreg-to-prepreg probe tack test fixture was developed in house:
 - Relatively large contact area (1"x1")
 - UD or Fabric testing
 - Testing prepregs at relative angles (0-0, 0-90, 0-45, ...)
 - Control over process parameters:
 - Temperature
 - Cohesion Pressure
 - Dwell time
 - Separation rate
 - Moisture
 - ...

Prepreg Tack

Characterization Tests

Approach
Force Controlled

Dwell
Constant Pressure & Temperature

Separation
Displacement Controlled

Prepreg Tack Constitutive Model

Cohesion Model

Decohesion Model

Degree of Intimate Contact:

$$I = e^{-\frac{\log\left(\frac{F}{F_{max}}\right)}{2I_{SD}^2}}$$

where F is the pressure flow index

$$F = \int \frac{P(t)}{\mu(X, T)} dt$$

$$\sigma_1 = R\sigma_{1VE}$$

Viscoelastic
Cohesive model for
decohesion stage

$$\sigma_{1u-r} = \sigma_{1u-r} e^{-\left(\frac{\Delta t}{\tau}\right)}$$

$$+ I(E_u - E_r) \left(\frac{\delta_n}{h}\right) \left(\frac{\tau}{\Delta t}\right) \left(1 - e^{-\left(\frac{\Delta t}{\tau}\right)}\right)$$

$$R = e^{-\left(\frac{(\delta - \delta_i)}{\delta_c}\right)^\gamma} \leq 1.0$$

Probe Tack

Model Fit Example

Shear Mechanisms

Transverse Shear

In-plane Fabric

Common Component Architecture (CCA)

Comprehensive Library of Material Constitutive Models

State-variable based, expandable material model database

Integrated **MATERIAL PROPERTIES**

- **140+** constitutive models
- Largest high-fidelity process simulation composite materials library anywhere:
 - **30+** open data sets
 - **10+** Distribution C data sets (created for and managed on behalf of the US Government)
 - **Many more** proprietary data sets created for customers
- Interlinked process parameters
- User-defined Constitutive Models

Simulation Framework

Shell Element

Ply In-plane: A stiffness

Ply Bending: D stiffness

Contact Algorithm

Interlaminar (friction, stick-slip, tack)

Tool-Part interaction

Solid + Shell Element[†]

Ply Transverse Shear & Logrolling

Debulk & Consolidation

Forming Simulation Solution Levels

Solution Level	FE Representation	Application	Features	Solver	Computational Cost
1	Single Membrane	Dry fabric forming	Shear locking	Explicit	Fast
2	Ply-wise Shell	Hot Drape Prepreg Forming <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effect of temperature and evolving degree-of-cure/crystallization • Effect of forming rate 	Level 1 + <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-plane / bending decoupling • Elastic/Viscoelastic behaviour • Temperature and DoC dependencies 	Explicit	Fast to Moderately Expensive
3	Ply-wise Shell + PU Solid (optional thermal analysis coupling)	Cross-section Prepreg Forming <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level 2 + • Consolidation & wrinkling • Non-uniform temperature/cure 	Level 2 + <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Debulk and consolidation • Resin flow • Thermal predictions 	Implicit Dynamic	Expensive

Shell-based Simulation

C-Channel Example

- Plies modelled using shells
- Inter-ply interaction through contact
- Representation of the tool, double bag/membrane, and stiffening elements

Bookending Effect

Fibre Axial Strains show tension and compression in joggle area

Shell-Based Simulation

C-Channel Example

The room temperature forming process showed significant defects at the tool side of the corners

- Large predicted shear strains agree very well with experimental observations

At the optimal forming temperature, wrinkling at the corners is greatly reduced, as predicted by simulation

Shell + Solid Representation

Shell + Solid Sandwich

- Plies are discretized individually by a layer of solid elements superimposed with shell elements at the top and bottom surfaces
 - Solid element enables through-thickness deformation and Percolation Flow mechanisms
 - Shell elements are key to simulate ply buckling
- Contact interactions are defined between plies (optional)
- This approach can be used to predict forming and consolidation-driven ply movement and defects.
- Heat transfer analysis can be coupled as well.

Shell + Solid Representation

Solid Elements: Coupled Pore Fluid + Stress

- Ply bulk and shear behaviours and resin flow
- Two-phase (skeleton, resin) element formulation with stress tensor given by:

$$\bar{\sigma} = \sigma_{SK} - pI$$

- Added DOF: hydrostatic pressure of the resin phase (p)

- Resin flow governed Darcy's law:

$$q = \frac{K}{\eta} \nabla p$$

- Material Attributes:
 - Shear (G_{12}, G_{13}, G_{23})
 - Fiber bed compaction ($\sigma_{33} = f(\epsilon_{33})$)
 - Viscosity (η)
 - Permeability (K)

Shell + Solid Representation

Forming Simulation

Shell + Solid Representation

Ply Movement and Wrinkle Prediction

48-ply laminate formed using double diaphragm forming at room temperature

- Comparing shear pattern and wrinkle formation

Micrograph images provided by NRC

Shell + Solid Representation

Consolidation-Driven Wrinkles

- Curved sections generate pressure differentials between tool-side and bag-side surfaces of the laminate:
 - Convex corners lead to higher pressure and corner thinning (resin outflow)
 - Concave lead to lower pressure and corner thickening (resin inflow)
- As the laminate consolidates over a convex corner, the radius of the outer plies is reduced leading to excess fibre length.
- This excess length must be sheared out through either inter-ply or inter-ply shear mechanisms to avoid defects:
 - Consolidation simulation with constrained edges prevents shearing, thus leading to ply buckling.

Concluding Remarks

- A comprehensive framework for forming characterization and simulation was presented:
 - Key deformation mechanisms were identified.
 - Characterization tests were developed for uncured prepreg (Bending, Shear, Tack, ...).
 - Physics-based material constitutive models were developed to fit the observed data.
 - Finite Element Simulation framework developed at various levels:
 - Shell-based representation suitable for forming simulation
 - Shell + Solid representation suitable for modelling forming and consolidation
 - Accurate representation of the tool, forming apparatus and boundary conditions are essential for a high-fidelity forming simulation
 - It was shown that ply deformations and defects generated in FE simulations are consistent with observations of the experimental trials.